
As the nights draw in it's the perfect time to settle down somewhere cosy to read your November LNL newsletter. Opportunities for LNLs to work together, qualitative research resources and all aboard Project TIER. Enjoy!

In this issue...

- [LNL collaborative projects](#)
- [Qualitative Research](#)
- [Welcomes and goodbyes](#)
- [UKRN resources](#)
- [Resources provided by new LNL Tom Morley](#)
- [Other resources](#)
- [Podcast](#)
- [Reading recommendations](#)
- [All this could be yours](#)

LNL collaborative projects

LNLs Dave Smailes and Joe Corneli invite you to get involved in some ‘low intensity’ collaborative projects. These projects have two aims:

- Foster new collaborations/strengthen existing connections between LNLs.
- Develop projects that could be a starting point for future grant applications (for example UKRI Metascience scheme, if that reopens in summer 2025).

The projects should not require a great deal of resources, perhaps just a couple of hours of work a week and few hard deadlines. To start you off, Dave and Joe have added two projects to [this Google doc](#) if you are interested in either of these, please get in touch with Dave or Jo. If you have a project idea that you would like to collaborate on with other LNLs, please add it to the Google doc. Try to keep the description of your ideas brief (less than a page). Add each new project on a new page.

Deadline: Ideally, it would be great if new projects could be added to the Google doc by the evening of **Monday November 25th**. **Ahead of that date, feel free to email any LNLs who have proposed a project, so that some early conversations can take place.** At the **LNL meeting on December 3rd**, Dave will talk through the proposed projects and make a final call for collaborators and/or additional projects.

If you have any questions please contact Dave david.smailes@northumbria.ac.uk

Qualitative Research

[TIER2](#)

Working Group request

[TIER2](#) - Enhancing Trust, Integrity and Efficiency in Research through next-level Reproducibility - aims to boost knowledge on reproducibility, create tools, engage communities, implement interventions and policy across different contexts to increase re-use and overall quality of research results.

Nicki Lisa Cole ncole@know-center.at works on open qualitative research via the [TIER2](#) project. She has a small working group on open qualitative research, looking to scope and produce resources based on TIER2 project findings such as [The Relevance and Feasibility of Reproducibility](#). This might include teaching materials (they will engage with FORRT). The materials will be hosted on About - [The Embassy of Good Science](#). If you would like to be part of this working group please contact Nicki.

[Quala Lab resource](#)

Collaboration request

Quala Lab is a collaborative working group finding connections between the open science movement and qualitative and mixed methods research. The group meets weekly to discuss ongoing projects, the philosophy of open science, and current events inside and outside of academia. This website is still very much under construction, but please feel free to explore what is there and provide any feedback you might have. **They are currently seeking collaborators.**

Quala Lab now has a Google Group for general discussion about qualitative open science and an open qualitative methods textbook project. If you are interested in learning more about the open qualitative textbook project, please see their [onboarding document](#).

Photo credit: Laura_O Pixabay

Welcomes and goodbyes

Please welcome new LNLs joining UKRN, and thank you to those stepping out of the role to move onto other exciting opportunities! We try to report all changes but if we miss you, please let us know and we will include you in the next newsletter.

Please welcome:

[Geetika Jain](#), lecturer in Digital Transformation and the new LNL at Keele University.

Huge thanks, goodbye and good luck:

[Will Cawthorn](#) who is changing roles within the University of Edinburgh to become Institutional Lead. Congratulations Will!

We are currently looking for new LNLs within University of Exeter, University of Gloucestershire, University of Greenwich, and University of Sunderland. If you have relevant contacts there please let us know so we can follow up - contact@ukrn.org

UKRN resources

[Project TIER webinar](#)

This month Richard Ball from Haverford College, Pennsylvania, and Project TIER Executive Committee member, gave an overview of the Project TIER protocol. He was joined by Aneta Piekut, Senior Lecturer in Quantitative Social Sciences, University of Sheffield who gave her reflections on co-hosting a previous TIER/UKRN workshop.

The TIER protocol uses a consistent directory format, each contains 2 files (a readme file and a report file) and 3 folders (data, scripts, outputs). The protocol is software neutral. There was discussion around how to use the TIER protocol with students. Please feel free to contact Richard at [Project TIER](#) to learn more.

Aneta said: It is great to build a community and share ideas for small reproducibility exercises through the event and Richard's workshop helps you to get the student experience of different ways of coding and encountered issues - I recommend it a lot!

If you would like more information on Aneta's syllabus and slides please feel free to [contact her](#).

The [webinar is now available](#) on the [UKRN YouTube channel](#) alongside a host of other UKRN resources.

[LNL guidebook](#)

The guidebook can help LNLs better understand the role of an LNL and its many benefits, and plan objectives and activities. There are also top tips, insights and personal reflections from current LNLs. The guidebook is now available as a [preprint](#).

[Email signature](#)

As UKRN Local Network Lead you are a great asset to research culture within your institution. We have created a short guide on using text and the UKRN logo within your email signature to promote your LNL role. Read it [here](#).

Resources provided by new LNL Tom Morley

[Guide to Publishing Open Access Monographs, Books, Book Chapters and Long-form Outputs](#)

A resource that is also a course! Lancaster University Library has launched a [new guide](#) to support authors interested in publishing open access books, monographs, book chapters, and edited collections. The guide covers a wide range of topics related to publishing open access books and includes a range of case studies with Lancaster authors, detailed guidance on topics such as licensing, and useful resources to support users to make informed decisions.

The resource can either be used as a reference guide to find information related to a specific topic, or users can work through each section in turn to help them better understand key considerations when publishing an open access book and to develop their publication strategy.

[Trailblazers](#)

Trailblazers is built upon collaboration and knowledge-sharing between the libraries of Lancaster University, University of Liverpool, University of Salford, and the publisher Liverpool University Press. It combines Open Access book publication, to maximise the opportunity for impact from early career research, with a series of author boot camps, which will equip Early Career Researchers with the knowledge and skills to support the publication of their work throughout their careers.

Huge thanks to Tom for sharing these. If you have resources you would like to promote through this newsletter please get in touch: contact@ukrn.org

Other resources

[The Embassy of Good Science](#)

The Embassy aims to become a unique 'go to' place, a public square where the community of researchers can gather to discuss 'hot topics', share knowledge, and find guidance and support to perform science responsibly and with integrity.

[Open Library of Humanities](#)

Publisher of humanities scholarship based at Birkbeck, University of London. They publish 33 open-access journals and are funded by more than 345 libraries worldwide. Journal topics include classics, modern languages, philosophy, theology, history, political theory, sociology, anthropology, film and new media studies, and digital humanities.

[Climate Coalition toolkit](#)

This is another quick plug for the digital humanities climate coalition toolkit. It is a guide to making your research practices more environmentally responsible. It is geared towards digital practices, but also touches on general areas such as travel and advocacy. It is a community-developed work-in-progress, and you are warmly invited to contribute. For more information please feel free to contact the University of Salford LNL Sharon Coen or members of the Climate Toolkit team Lisa Otty (University of Edinburgh) and Christopher Ohge (University of London). Learn more [here](#) and join their email list. As Sharon says, engaging with the toolkit is an opportunity to '*save the planet as well as the dignity of science.*'

Podcast

The Storyology Podcast

The Storyology Podcast investigates what happens when science meets story. Hosted by materials scientist and storyteller Dr Anna Ploszajski, each episode tracks the effects, risks, limitations and opportunities of communicating science with story. The podcast gathers evidence from experts along the way, as we track the presence of story along the whole pipeline of how science gets communicated; from funding to publication to the media and the general public. If you want to understand how two of the strongest forces in

society affect our everyday lives - from GP appointments to justice - this is the podcast for you.

This podcast is made in partnership with the UK Reproducibility Network and University of the Arts London, and is funded through [StoryArcs](#), which is an Arts and Humanities Research Council funded project based at Bath Spa University.

The first episode was released on Friday 1 November.

Apple Podcasts: <https://podcasts.apple.com/gb/podcast/the-storyology-podcast/id1777046234>

Spotify: <https://open.spotify.com/show/2HQLq1T8RoxGbo9DoqNJ5z>

Amazon music: <https://music.amazon.co.uk/podcasts/b32348d3-e1e7-4ea8-83a4-949e8598814a/the-storyology-podcast>

Reading recommendations

[Promoting reusable and open methods and protocols \(PRO-MaP\) can improve methodological reporting in the life sciences](#)

Detailed method descriptions are essential for reproducibility, research evaluation, and effective data reuse. This paper summarises the key recommendations for life sciences researchers and research institutions described in the European Commission PRO-MaP report.

[The academic impact of Open Science: a scoping review](#)

Thomas Klebel and colleagues use the PRISMA scoping review methodology to explore the academic impacts of Open Science including citations, quality, efficiency, equity, reuse, ethics, and reproducibility.

[Ten simple rules for structuring papers](#)

This is a relatively old paper now but still contains useful advice from authors Brett Mensh and Konrad Kording.

All this could be yours

Would you like to contribute articles? Get in touch and we'll support you in making it a reality contact@ukrn.org